

**D5.8 Third annual report on
dissemination activities to
international stakeholders**

**WP5 Science to Policy
Translation to stakeholders**

Responsible Partner: BfR, SSI

Contributing partners: PMT members

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1. Summary

This report describes the dissemination activities of WP5 – Science to Policy Translation of One Health EJP during Y3. Two Stakeholders Committee meetings were held, and dissemination activities followed the established strategy (D5.5). Reach out to European and international stakeholders was successfully broadened. At the same time, the links to national stakeholders across the EU were strengthened, e.g. at the POC-PMC meeting.

2. Highlights

Top achievements:

- Building on the dialogue initiated in Y2 and following the ongoing global reach out strategy, the Stakeholders Committee was successfully enlarged with the inclusion of additional European Agencies and International Organizations.
- Outcomes of WP5 were presented to the POC-PMC (Directors General of the beneficiaries, representatives of the relevant Ministries of authority), the Scientific Steering Board, the External Scientific Advisory Board and at various other meetings.
- Representatives of ECDC, EFSA, OIE and WHO-EURO gave testimonies regarding their interactions with and expectations from the One Health EJP at the PMC-POC meeting.
- WP5 collaborated successfully with the One Health EJP coordinators for the enlargement campaign of the consortium. At least six new partners are joining at the beginning of 2021, broadening the EU Member States represented in the One Health EJP.
- The One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI, formerly “capacity map”) was launched and provides now up-to-date outcomes of the consortium to internal and external audiences.

3. Description of the activities

Dissemination is defined as follows: “The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.” (EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms). Dissemination activities aim at making results and outputs available as widely as possible so that they can be used by others. Dissemination is thus disclosure of the results in an attractive and user-friendly way. Targeted dissemination focuses on specific audiences that can make best use of the results, this gaining impact.

WP5 dissemination activities are complementary to the general dissemination activities of the One Health EJP (WP1, Communications Team). Both teams ensure that scientific publications and other One Health EJP outcomes are quickly made available on the website of the One Health EJP and on the European OpenAIRE program Zenodo (WP1). Stakeholders are encouraged to use these materials, and their usage is promoted during formal contacts. For example the targeted reports, distributed every six months to ECDC and EFSA in the form of clickable pdf files, do not only report scientific progress, but also facilitate linkage with the One Health EJP website, social media, and with projects’ webpages and resources.

WP5 dissemination activities address specific groups, including Stakeholders Committee, Project Management Team, Communications Team, Project Leaders and other specific stakeholders. The activities focus largely on facilitating diffusion and use of knowledge. Transactional aspects, linking the providers and users of the knowledge, are also included. Moreover, there are social change aspects: the EJP advocates One Health approach by enhancing and facilitating access and use of the One Health EJP results.

Stakeholders Committee

During Y3, the dissemination activities of WP5 focused on the members of the **Stakeholders Committee**: Key EU Stakeholders ECDC and EFSA, other EU Stakeholders EEA and EMA, and global organisations FAO, OIE and WHO-EURO. Moreover, focus was directed towards the national stakeholders, which will feature more in the focus of Y4.

The Stakeholders Committee meets twice per year at the **Stakeholders Committee meetings (SCMs)**, which are organised in conjunction with major One Health EJP events in order to ease the participation of the stakeholders in these events. In Y3, the 5th SCM (on the 26th of May 2020) took place the day before the ASM, and the 6th SCM (on the 12th of October 2020) the day before the POC-PMC meeting. Due to the COVID-19 situation, all meetings of Y3 were virtual meetings.

The SCMs are organized to foster interaction with the Key EU Stakeholders, international stakeholders, as well as with relevant EU-funded projects. In Y3 the major goals of the SCMs were:

- to ensure that One Health EJP is aware of relevant research needs and expectations of European and global stakeholders,
- to discuss the most effective ways for the One Health EJP to have impact,
- to discuss the most effective ways for the stakeholders to pick up and use the outcomes of the One Health EJP,
- to disseminate results and outcomes of the One Health EJP in a targeted manner.

Building on contacts initiated in Y2, new members joined the SCMs: EU organisations EEA and EMA and global organisations FAO and WHO-EURO joined the 5th SCM, and OIE joined the 6th SCM. The Stakeholders Committee is thus now composed of:

- Key EU Stakeholders: ECDC and EFSA
- EU agencies: EEA and EMA
- Global organisations: FAO, OIE, WHO-EURO
- EU funded projects: EU-JAMRAI and JPIAMR

This composition is considered to be optimal, balancing EU and global stakeholders, the animal, human, food and environmental sectors, and allowing interaction with relevant EU projects. The composition allows fruitful and focused discussion, as well as building trust among the organisations' representatives and between them and the One Health EJP.

Due to internal re-organisation at ECDC, during Y2 the One Health EJP contact person at ECDC could not continue her engagement. Transition was complicated by the pressing commitments linked with the COVID-19 response of the new contact. Informal communication was initiated via email

and phone, and the new contact person was fully engaged by the 6th Stakeholders Committee meeting (SCM) and the POC-PMC meeting.

Dissemination mechanisms

To maximise dissemination to the stakeholders, stakeholder organisations' representatives participated and gave presentations at major events of the One Health EJP, for example at the Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM, from the 27th to the 29th of May 2020). In addition, representatives of ECDC, EFSA, OIE and WHO-EURO gave testimonies regarding their interactions with and expectations from the One Health EJP at the **Programme Owners Committee (POC) - Programme Managers Committee (PMC) joint meeting**.

The POC-PMT meeting is a high level meeting of the One Health EJP addressed at national risk managers, decision makers and policy makers. In the meeting, the PMT met with the Programme Managers (i.e. Directors General of the beneficiaries) and Programme Owners (i.e. representatives of the relevant Ministries of authority), and highlighted the outcomes of the One Health EJP and the impact that it can have at the national level. A section of the meeting was dedicated to the achievements of WP5. This event launched the next focus of the WP5 dissemination, where national stakeholders are targeted, while the main focus continues to be on the Key EU Stakeholders.

Outcomes of WP5 were additionally disseminated by poster presentations and oral presentations given

- at events organised by the One Health EJP, including the ASM 2020, the Summer School 2020, and the two SCMs
- at events organised by the stakeholders, and after invitation by the stakeholders, including EFSA's Parma Summer School (presentation) and the JPIAMR-CONNECT meeting (presentation),
- at international conferences like the World One Health Congress (a dedicated hub of the One Health EJP and several posters and presentations).

These presentations received attention also in social media (e.g. [here](#) and [here](#))

WP5 dissemination activities were not limited to the dissemination of research outcomes. In collaboration with the Communications Team (WP1), ASM organisers (WP3) and with the Education and Training Team (WP6), WP5 disseminated information on ASM and education and training activities organised by the One Health EJP (e.g. Summer School 2020, Continuing Professional Development module 2020) to the stakeholders. Moreover, WP5 provided **VIP participation** to stakeholders.

Dissemination activities of WP5 are not unilateral. The information not only flows from the One Health EJP to the stakeholders' organisations, and it is then distributed within the organisations, but the One Health EJP vast network is also made available to the stakeholders. This **dissemination from stakeholders to the One Health EJP** was not limited to supporting the stakeholders by distribution of information, but went further by creating new links and interactions. During Y3 two major examples of this dissemination were the JPIAMR's CONNECT survey and the WHO Global Outbreak Alert and Response Network (GOARN) Request for Assistance.

The CONNECT survey was disseminated to our network (at the end of Y2), and this resulted in the invitation of the One Health EJP to the JPIAMR-CONNECT meeting, where results of the survey were discussed as well as further interactions between the One Health EJP and JPIAMR.

Interaction with the WHO-GOARN was initiated by an invitation to distribute the WHO-GOARN Request for Assistance within the One Health EJP network. The One Health EJP subsequently joined the WHO-GOARN as partner, and WP5 started a collaborative project with the WHO-GOARN and with the One Health Commission, a global survey on the topic of One Health workforce contribution to the COVID-19 response.

Reports

To keep the Key European Stakeholders up to date with the scientific and integrative output of the One Health EJP, two **Targeted Reports to Key EU Stakeholders** were produced and disseminated, containing brief updates on projects of particular interest for ECDC and EFSA, as well as general achievements of the consortium. The targeted reports are clickable pdf files that link with external resources, and support contacts with persons in charge of specific outcomes. The reports were

distributed one month before each SCM. The targeted reports were then disseminated within the stakeholders' organisations to relevant colleagues. The feedback received from the stakeholders on the targeted reports was very positive.

Considering the stakeholders' needs gathered during the SCMs and during the WP5 activity scanning of stakeholders' documents (described below), two **thematic reports** were published. The first report, "Links between COVID-19 related needs of stakeholders and One Health EJP activities", focused on One Health EJP COVID-19 response actions, and highlighted the responsiveness and timeliness of the One Health EJP. To minimise the risk of duplication of efforts and maximise added value, alignment of One Health EJP activities to international research needs was analysed and summarised. The second report, "One Health EJP Thematic Report on AMR", provided an overview of the key outcomes and publications produced by the One Health EJP projects (joint research projects, joint integrative projects and PhD projects) in the field of AMR.

To maximise visibility, the two thematic reports were published on the One Health EJP website, where a dedicated section was established for WP5 reports (<https://onehealthejp.eu/science-to-policy-translation/>), uploaded on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/record/4047856> and <https://zenodo.org/record/4047866>) and disseminated by a number of means, including direct mails to the stakeholders, presented at the SCMs, and shared with the Scientific Steering Board of the One Health EJP.

Enlargement campaign

WP5 gave major input to the **enlargement campaign** of the One Health EJP, which aimed ideally at the representation of all EU Member States (MSs) in the consortium. One Health EJP partner countries should be represented by one organisation responsible for the public health side and one for the animal health side in order to ensure a good One Health balance.

WP5 drafted a prioritisation protocol based on criteria set by the coordination of the One Health EJP. A detailed list of organisations suitable for membership was drafted for all the EU countries not yet participating in the One Health EJP, as well as for the countries which lacked the representation of either the public health or the animal health side. The list included a number of information for each

organisation (e.g. relevant contacts, national reference roles, ECDC/EFSA national focal point, ECDC/EFSA networks) and consisted of 82 potential partners from 15 EU MSs not yet part of the One Health EJP, and from countries members of the consortium, but lacking representation of the public health or the animal health side. The potential partners were shortlisted to 24 and contacted with the invitation to join the One Health EJP.

Online meetings were organized with the responding candidate partners to introduce the One Health EJP and to explain the advantages of joining, as well as what is expected from the new partners. Moreover, these online meetings served to establish contacts and to disseminate examples of the impact and of outcomes produced by the consortium.

This work is ongoing. At the moment (December 2020) at least six new partner institutions are joining the One Health EJP. The involvement of WP5 in the process provides a good basis for establishing dissemination to the national stakeholders in the new joining countries.

Scanning of stakeholders' documents

WP5 carries on regular **scanning of stakeholders' documents** (scanning around 50 webpages of relevant institutions like EC, EEA, EFSA, ECDC, EMA, DG-SANTE, FAO, OIE, WHO) in order to identify relevant new research and integrative needs of stakeholders and establish interactions where complementarity may be feasible. Information extracted following this process is summarised in monthly reports and made available to the One Health EJP consortium members and to the stakeholders by uploading the reports in the private groups of the One Health EJP website.

If pressing information is identified it is timely communicated, before the publication of the monthly report, to the PMT, Project Leaders, or Communications Team to support their means of dissemination (e.g. social media). One example of interaction initiated as a result of this scanning activity and in collaboration with the WP2 - Integrative Strategic Research Agenda of the One Health EJP, is the interaction with the newly funded Zoonotic Disease Integrated Action initiative (ZODIAC) of the International Atomic Energy Agency.

The One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI)

The activities of the One Health EJP consortium are numerous and diverse. WP5 makes sure that its results are made readily available for policy and decision making through targeted dissemination to the stakeholders. In addition, WP5 curates the **One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI)**.

Briefly, the OHOI is an online database inventorying and cataloguing the outcomes of 24 Joint Research Projects, 5 Joint Integrative Projects, 17 PhD projects and overarching activities of the One Health EJP. It is available from the One Health EJP website (<https://onehealthejp.eu/outcome-inventory/>).

The OHOI is a tool linking the stakeholders' needs with the scientific and integrative results of the consortium. It highlights outcomes of the One Health EJP, supports dissemination of results of the various activities (e.g. research projects, integrative activities), and depicts to some extent complementarity with activities outside the One Health EJP. The OHOI is a public online database accessible to all. As such it targets also stakeholders not represented in the Stakeholders Committee, and supports internal and external collaboration and dissemination. The OHOI has been already recognized as a valuable tool for dissemination of results of the One Health EJP to national and international stakeholders, to other One Health initiatives, as well as within the One Health EJP, to minimize the risk of duplication of work.

The OHOI was formerly known as “outcome inventory”, but given that its scope was focused in Y2 (see D5.7), it was renamed following consultation within the PMT. The OHOI is organized into an Outcome section and an Updates section. Both the Outcome and the Updates section have a search function to ease navigation and to browse the inventory.

The Outcome section lists the outcome of the consortium (databases, biobanks, computational methods, pieces of hardware, etc.), gives general information on the specific outcome, highlights the added value by depicting to a certain extent similar activities in place outside of the consortium, and links to specific resources if available. Most importantly it includes the contact information of the persons in charge, facilitating contacts in case more insights are desired.

The Updates section illustrates the progress of the different areas covered in the OHOI in a timely manner. It provides updates on the activities of projects which are completed, in progress or planned, with reference to the source material where the information was acquired. If an update deals with a specific outcome, there is a link to the Outcome section of the OHOI. Contacts of the persons responsible for the update are also given.

To populate the OHOI, in Y3 WP5 summarised information on the outcomes from deliverables, reports, publications, and personal communications. The gathered information was validated by the project leaders and by the PMT, and uploaded online in a relational database.

Two major updates of the database were performed during Y3, as well as ad hoc updates as new information became available and needed to be disseminated. The first major update consisted of around 520 entries, the second update of around 350 entries.

In addition to the design, population of the database, deployment, update and technical curation, WP5 gathered feedback from the users and improved the OHOI accordingly.

Information of the OHOI was disseminated:

- to the stakeholders during the SCMs,
- internally through the newsletter,
- externally through presentation in One Health EJP events (e.g. ASM, POC-PMC meeting, SSB meeting) and at international conferences (e.g. World One Health Congress, EFSA Summer School)

WP5 is also part of the **Data Management Plan (DMP)** committee of One Health EJP, which supports Project Leaders to draft their respective DMPs. During Y3, an online software was chosen as the tool to facilitate the work of the projects, and discussion is ongoing with the company that provides the software to link the DMPs with the outcomes listed in the OHOI.

Bilateral interactions

WP5 facilitates **bilateral interactions** between projects and stakeholders. These interactions are a way for the projects to discuss their strategy, progress, synergy with the stakeholders' projects, and to disseminate their outcomes to targeted audience at stakeholders' organisations. To create the basis for an effective interaction from the very beginning of the projects, representatives of ECDC and EFSA participated in the Kick-off Meetings of a number of 2nd call projects.

Following stakeholders' advice, these interactions were mapped in Y3. Bilateral interactions were found to be particularly effective when contact officers responsible for the interaction with One Health EJP project of interest were appointed (this is the case for some stakeholders' organisations like EFSA, ECDC and FAO). Gaps were identified and WP5 offered support to strengthen the communication between stakeholders and projects. In collaboration with WP3 - Joint Research Projects (JRPs) and WP4 - Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs), WP5 discussed the possibility of organising dissemination workshops focused on specific topics and targeted to specific stakeholders.

In addition, in order to continue strengthening links with key stakeholders, WP5 has established contact with the Head of ECDC's fellowship training programme in order to increase awareness of the OHEJP projects carried out at ECDC fellowship training sites and to highlight the importance of cross-disciplinary and One Health topics during the fellowship programmes.

Main dissemination plans for Year 4

WP5 dissemination activities will continue actively in Y4, and they build on the established connections and success of the activities in Y1-Y3. Newly upcoming results for research projects and integrative activities will be disseminated using the means described in the dissemination strategy (D5.5). The next major dissemination activity will be the third ASM in 2021 (from the 9th to the 11th of June 2021) and the 7th and 8th SCM. In addition, discussion with WP3 and WP4 is ongoing on the organisation of targeted dissemination workshops. More focus will be placed on active dissemination to national stakeholders, while the key links to Key EU Stakeholders and Stakeholders Committee are maintained.

During Y4 the full OHOI will be updated twice by WP5, and following users' requests as they come up. The OHOI will also be linked with the DMP.

Following stakeholders identified needs, one targeted report will be produced in Y4 on environmental issues. It will be disseminated to the target audiences, the stakeholders' organisations, and it will also be made public.

Some activities of WP5 deal with the issues of long-term sustainability and future needs of stakeholders. To reach maximum impact of results and to avoid duplication of efforts, WP5 will collaborate with WP2 - Integrative Strategic Research Agenda (SRIA) and with WP7 - Sustainability. Information on policy and research needs of stakeholders are gathered by WP5 through contacts with EU and global organisations represented in the Stakeholders Committee, and through regular scanning of stakeholders documents. These activities could inform WP2 in drafting the SRIA. Information on new EU policy initiatives could support the efforts of WP7 on the sustainability of the consortium. Initial web meetings were held already during Y3 and collaboration will be strengthened in Y4.

The planning and organisation of the stakeholders meeting, to be held in Y5, will largely happen during Y4. The event will focus on dissemination of results to decision makers and policy makers.

4. Evaluation, impact and potential

WP5 - Science to Policy Translation was active and successful in its dissemination activities during Y3. The structures for efficient dissemination are in place, in use, and were further adjusted and refined based on dialogue with the Stakeholders. Maintaining dialogue with Key EU stakeholders, going global and widening the Stakeholders Committee, enlargement campaign of the One Health EJP, and launch of focus on national stakeholders at the joint POC-PMC meeting were successful.

The dissemination activities of WP5 received positive feedback from the stakeholders during SCM meetings and were highlighted by the European and international stakeholders at the POC-PMC meeting of national stakeholders. Efficient uptake and use of the results maximizes the impact of the projects and, in general, of the One Health EJP.

5. Attachments

- Thematic Report “Links between COVID-19 related needs of stakeholders and One Health EJP activities”, downloadable from <https://zenodo.org/record/4047856>
- Thematic Report “One Health EJP Thematic Report on AMR”, downloadable from <https://zenodo.org/record/4047866>
- WP5 - Science to Policy Translation dissemination page on the One Health EJP website, <https://onehealthejp.eu/science-to-policy-translation/>

